

OCTAPUS: Empowering Next Generation Central Offices with Cross-Layer Network Intelligence towards a Reconfigurable Data Plane

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Abstract. Considering the challenges faced by the current Central Offices, this paper presents a novel architecture and related technological aspects of the Next Generation Central Offices (NGCOs), as envisioned within the OCTAPUS research project, towards the flexible support of the emerging capacity and latency demanding services. First, the main functional blocks of the OCTAPUS NGCO Data and Control planes are presented, with emphasis on the dynamicity of the optical paths within the NGCO and its reconfiguration capabilities. Then, focusing on the Control plane, we describe in detail its hierarchical structure, the role of the associated entities and the interactions among them. An example of network provisioning to support multiple concurrent next-generation services of realistic use cases in a real urban area is used to stress the need for NGCOs to adapt to different service requirements and temporal fluctuations in traffic demands, while catering for time-sensitive services with stringent delay requirements.

Keywords: Next Generation Central Office, Programmable Control Plane, OCTAPUS Use Cases, Network provisioning.

1 Introduction

The continuing popularity of Over-The-Top (OTT) video streaming services and the emergence of Machine-to-Machine (M2M) communications have been the main drivers behind the unabated rise in the demand for fixed/mobile network capacity. Emerging 5G and Industrial Internet applications, classified as “Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications (URLLC)”, also introduce a new latency-oriented framework that challenges the current network infrastructure and motivates radical architectural changes at the Central Offices (COs), which constitutes the closest to the subscribers traffic aggregation point [1]. To this end, network operators are considering exploiting virtualization and Software Defined Networking (SDN) technologies to restructure the traditional CO architecture and bring it closer to that of a mini data center supporting automatic service provisioning and orchestration [2], thus targeting flexible and efficient service rollout with lower Capital/Operational Expenditure and shorter time-to-market. At the same time, a close examination of the CO anatomy reveals additional unresolved issues that must be addressed by the NGCOs:

- Although switching capacity of the Optical Line Terminal (OLT) side is still the primary enabler for many fixed/mobile access technologies, recent state-of-the-art CO-grade switches are not future-proof and even the most advanced datacenter-grade switches struggle to offer switching capacity above 51.2Tbps [3]. Also, conventional OLTs employ an electrical backplane, which suffers from high power consumption and latency incurred by the SerDes and DSP interfaces.
- The OLT’s electrical backplane typically provides static i.e., non-configurable, non-scalable connectivity between Uplink Switches (facing the metro network) and Interface (IF) cards (facing the access network), as the OLT chassis crucially limits the number of IF cards. Attractive features such as load balancing and bandwidth steering would require ultra-high-speed electrical switches beyond current technological capabilities, while also adding further store-and-forward delay.
- With the ITU-T 50G-Passive Optical Network (PON) standard being released in September 2021 (and amended in September 2022 [4]), along with the allocation of the relevant wavelength bands, there is a clear need to equip the NGCO’s access-side IF cards with energy- and cost-efficient 50G O-band transceivers.
- Despite the growing maturity of the SDN technologies, progress in consolidation of the software controllers with the underlying NGCO physical layer (and particularly the optical layer interfaces) remains an open issue with vendors providing, at best, limited proprietary controllers [5].
- The 5G Radio Access Network (RAN) disaggregation into distinct Central Unit (CU), Distributed Unit (DU) and Remote Unit (RU) entities has introduced two major challenges: i) the need for coexistence of multiple different types of fronthaul/midhaul/backhaul (i.e., X-haul) traffic, with disparate throughput, latency, and jitter requirements and ii) the increased distance between CU/DU and RU exacerbates the limited delay budget of time-critical applications and requires that the NGCO supports deterministic latency bound guarantees in the spirit of the Time Sensitive Networking (TSN) family of standards [6]. For more latency-stringent applications, where even standard store-and-forward packet processing may introduce unacceptable delays, there is currently no mechanism within COs for creating

“Express” paths that would bypass most active equipment and directly interconnect TSN service endpoints with the minimum possible latency.

Inspired by the OCTAPUS Horizon Europe project [7], this paper presents a holistic solution to the above capacity/latency/configurability predicament, as enabled by an intelligent, programmable Control Plane (CP) that exploits novel hardware capabilities to offer the necessary reconfigurability features in the Data Plane (DP) and support the demanding new use cases.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the architecture and functional blocks of the OCTAPUS NGCO, with emphasis on how the programmable CP addresses the above challenges. Section 3 presents a quantitative analysis of a synthetic use case to illustrate how the OCTAPUS NGCO can adapt to different network fixed and mobile traffic fluctuations and latency requirements. Section 4 concludes the paper.

2 Overview of the OCTAPUS NGCO solution

2.1 NGCO architecture and functional blocks

The OCTAPUS NGCO (see Fig. 1), consists of the following main components in the Data plane:

Fig. 1. OCTAPUS NGCO Control and Data Plane.

Uplink Switches (ULS) and Interface (IF) cards: these elements serve the same purpose as in legacy COs, with the Uplink Switches providing the interface towards the metro network and the IF cards serving the NGCO’s downstream subscribers (e.g., Passive Optical Network (PON) line cards, 4G/5G Base Stations or disaggregated RUs). To serve the bandwidth demanding OCTAPUS use cases, the ULSs and IF cards have

high port densities (256 and 16 ports are provisioned per ULS and IF, respectively) to achieve huge aggregate capacities of 25.6 Tbps and 800 Gbps (per device), respectively, utilizing high-speed 50 Gbps transceivers at each port. Furthermore, all ULSs and IF cards support specific TSN features, enabling ultra-low-latency demanding applications, as described below.

Low-power 50 Gbps transceivers: these are employed by the ULSs and IF cards and combine novel O-band Indium Phosphide (InP)-based Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs) with low-power driver and TransImpedance Amplifier (TIA) Electronic Integrated Circuits (EICs) to support the key feature of burst-mode operation required for High Speed PON (HS-PON) [8].

Reconfigurable Optical Circuit Switching (OCS) backplane: OCTAPUS employs an SDN-controllable, reconfigurable, all-optical OCS backplane consisting of multiple O-band, low-loss, 2x2 non-volatile (i.e., zero power is required to maintain its switching state and the light path after its establishment through the switch) photonic switching devices on a SiN platform with nanosecond-scale reconfiguration times. Each 2x2 optical switching device exploits the novel properties of Phase Change Materials (PCM) [9] to achieve 2 different non-blocking switching states by properly driving the device's heating circuits to change the PCM material state between crystalline and amorphous. The dynamic OCS controllability allows for efficient load balancing among the ULSs while the modularity of the OCS, being essentially composed of multiple 2x2 optical switches, offers inherent scalability for ULS and IF cards, allowing for higher number than the ones shown in Fig. 1.

Express paths: these are dedicated paths, limited in number (e.g., 32 Express paths in Fig. 1) and targeting C-band operation for PON support, bypassing all active components of the NGCO and the OCS and directly connecting the metro network with the appropriate end-node (i.e., Optical Network Unit, 5G RU) on the access side of the IF card to serve the most time-critical traffic, whose latency budget necessitates the elimination of any unnecessary processing. Low functional split fronthaul, such as eCPRI (enhanced Common Public Radio Interface) 7.2 split or even legacy CPRI [10], is a prime example of traffic that benefits from these Express paths. Their hardware implementation is based on the PCM switching devices to develop a tree-switch layout, while the actual decision of whether a light path should be established through the NGCO proper or the (bypass) Express paths is made by the Wavelength Selective Switching (WSS) device, also shown in the left side of Fig. 1.

O/C-band diplexers and low-loss coupling interfaces to SiN and InP PICs: low-loss, glass-based 1340/1550nm optical diplexers are employed at the InP transceivers of the IF cards, (shown on the right hand side of Fig. 1) to allow O-band PON traffic to pass through the NGCO from the access side (in the upstream) while also routing C-band traffic towards one of the above Express paths, in an all-passive manner. The diplexers are integrated with Waveguide Array to Fiber Transposer (WAFT)-based interposers to provide low loss PIC-to-fiber coupling interfaces [11].

TSN-enabled ULSs and IF cards: the incorporation of TSN features, such as network-wide synchronization (via the gPTP profile in IEEE 802.1AS [12]) and scheduled transmissions via Time-aware shapers (according to IEEE 802.1Qbv [13]), into the Up-link switches and IF cards, offers important benefits in terms of deterministic delivery

and achieved latency guarantees, flow-prioritization, low bounded delay, thus enabling applications with very tight delay budgets. The management of the TSN flows requires additional CP entities as described below.

In addition to the above DP entities, the following software-implemented entities constitute the OCTAPUS NGCO Control Plane (CP):

Central User Configuration (CUC): it collects the TSN traffic stream requests and their corresponding requirements, in terms of End-to-End (E2E) throughput and latency, so that a suitable schedule satisfying these requirements can be constructed. The CUC is embedded into the multi-domain SDN Coordinator described below.

Central Network Controller (CNC): it receives the above information from the CUC, along with network topology information, and computes the routed path for each TSN flow (only), as well as the actual transmission schedule for each TSN node, in terms of proper transmission windows. Any remaining transmissions windows are then available to serve standard (i.e., Best Effort (BE)) Ethernet traffic. Once the CNC determines the actual TSN path and schedule, it sends configuration messages to all TSN nodes, including the Uplink switches and IF cards.

Multi-domain SDN Coordinator: this is the overall “brain” of the OCTAPUS NGCO and hosts all network intelligence to coordinate higher layer functions (e.g., power/congestion-aware routing for BE traffic, load balancing) based on network state information obtained through consistent monitor. The SDN Coordinator employs a hierarchical structure with two domain-specific controllers, the TSN CNC controller and the OCS SDN controller, which is responsible for initiating the OCS backplane reconfiguration.

The above OCTAPUS DP and CP framework may address all major challenges faced by current COs in terms of capacity scaling, backplane reconfigurability, power efficiency, while supporting deterministic latency guarantees along with the latest PON standard versions to enable the demanding, next-generation use cases. We next focus on the OCTAPUS CP, which coordinates all the abovementioned functional blocks.

2.2 SDN-driven Control plane

Since one of the main advantages of the OCTAPUS solution lies in its ability to handle the very strict latency requirements demanded by various 5G services, such as URLLC and/or fronthaul, which (in turn) necessitate the dynamic and proactive (re)configuration and monitoring of the different elements within the NGCO ecosystem, the OCTAPUS NGCO CP has a crucial role in supporting this functionality. To facilitate efficient handling of the NGCO resources, OCTAPUS has adopted a hierarchical approach that offers the following advantages:

- Different levels of granularity of the status of NGCO elements: A network operator can have a high-level perspective of the NGCO status but alternatively can also opt for a finer-granularity view of the specific NGCO elements (i.e. the OCS, IF cards, ULSs) based on the circumstances and overall needs.
- High degree of flexibility offered to the NGCO CP when dealing with different domains (e.g., TSN and OCS domains): This flexibility becomes extremely useful

when reconfiguring the NGCO, as it would involve interaction with only the relevant component of the NGCO CP (due to its hierarchical structure).

- Reduction of the costs of network management due to the automatic (re)configuration of the NGCO elements, since all actions that should be manually applied on the individual elements are now automatically executed by the NGCO CP.

The main components comprising the OCTAPUS NGCO CP are depicted in Fig. 2, which shows the OCS SDN Controller and the CNC being responsible for the control of the optical domain (i.e., the OCS within the light blue box in Fig. 1) and the TSN domain (i.e. the IF cards and the ULSs within the green boxes in Fig. 1), respectively. Then, on top of these two controllers, the SDN Coordinator and the CUC interact with them to collect and process the provided information. On the highest level of the NGCO CP, an NGCO “user” (i.e., a network operator or infrastructure owner) can interact with the NGCO CP, typically via a management interface, to configure the different services. The SDN Coordinator also interacts with TSN Talker(s) and Listener(s), i.e., the endpoints of TSN services running over the operator’s network, to collect TSN stream requirements and delegate their configurations and resource allocation to the CNC.

Fig. 2. NGCO Control Plane Functional Architecture.

The hierarchical structure of the NGCO CP in Fig. 2 offers all aforementioned benefits: i) each specific SDN Controller is responsible for and tailored to a specific domain, ii) there are different levels of abstraction hiding the technical complexity when desirable and iii) the architecture maintains a high degree of flexibility and modularity. More details on the role of the functional elements depicted in Fig. 2 and their interactions within the NGCO CP are provided below:

OCS SDN Agent: This functional component processes requests for configuring and monitoring the OCS, specifically the 2x2 PCM switches (PCMs) within it. The OCS SDN Agent touches upon both the Control Plane and the Data plane by configuring the optical circuit switching performed within the PCMs and updating their configurations. The main role of the OCS SDN Agent, which can be hosted in a Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA), is to process and translate the software-level configuration requests into hardware-level commands to be executed by the FPGA towards creating the

control waveforms to drive the actual PCM switch hardware. In the hierarchical NGCO CP architecture, the OCS SDN Agent mainly interacts with the OCS SDN Controller.

OCS SDN Controller: The OCS SDN Controller functional component is responsible for controlling the OCS domain. It mainly interacts with the OCS SDN Agent for the configuration and monitoring of the OCS, particularly its PCMs. The OCS SDN Controller, exploiting the information provided by the OCS SDN Agent, can analyze, abstract, and report such information to higher layers to facilitate OCS management. The OCS SDN Controller exposes its functionalities (i.e., the OCS information abstraction, configuration and monitoring) through its Northbound Interface (NBI).

CNC: It is responsible for the CP of the TSN domain. To this end, it executes custom algorithms to determine routes and transmission schedule tables for each TSN stream to ensure the Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, i.e., CNC ensures that those streams reach their destination even in the worst-case scenario. The CNC manages information related to the TSN topology, TSN flow requests and their associated lifecycle management. To provide its functionalities to the other TSN entities, it exposes interfaces used for TSN flow management (relying on the IEEE802.1Qdj specification [14]), while the information about the topology and resources is exposed through another proprietary interface. The CNC mainly interacts with the TSN network (i.e., TSN switches and endpoint Network Interface Cards, which receive the transmission/routing configuration parameters selected by the CNC) to reconfigure the topology and TSN flows and perform resource allocation while ensuring QoS. The transmission/routing configuration parameters adhere to the IEEE 802.1Qcw standard [15]. The CNC also interacts with the CUC and the SDN Coordinator, as described below.

SDN Coordinator and CUC: The SDN Coordinator represents the central entity of the NGCO CP interacting with other functional entities including i) the OCS SDN Controller, ii) the CNC and iii) the Management system. By collecting information and exploiting the functionalities offered by the two distinct SDN Controllers, the SDN Coordinator has an end-to-end view of the entire NGCO, being aware of both the logical and physical NGCO internal topology, overall resource allocations and the NGCO performance. Based on the above, the SDN coordinator can also balance the traffic between the ULSs towards preventing traffic congestion. According to the high-level requirements, the SDN Coordinator must be able to manage the lifecycle of different types of traffic within the NGCO. However, since the CNC must follow the IEEE802.1Qdj specification [14] for the TSN flow management model and User/Network Interface (UNI), this requires the CUC functionality to be logically embedded within the SDN Coordinator to offer the SDN Coordinator “access” to the TSN configuration and bridge the gap between these two different approaches of traffic and flow management. The CUC is indeed the entry point for receiving the stream requests coming from the TSN Talker(s) and Listener(s), i.e., the two network entities at the endpoints of the requested TSN transport service. From a functional perspective, including the CUC functional entity within the SDN Coordinator enables the SDN Coordinator to participate in the end-to-end TSN stream management.

Management System: On top of the SDN Coordinator, a functional component called “Management System” is available. This component represents the entry point for

either a network administrator or an NGCO “user” (e.g., an operator and/or service provider) and provides a user interface showing the information about the NGCO (i.e., topology, status, active flows, performance and so on) and offering functionalities for managing the different aspects of the NGCO CP e.g., NGCO status and monitoring, management of the different TSN and Best Effort (BE) flows. The Management System also processes and translates the requests coming from the network administrator into suitable requests for the SDN Coordinator.

Based on design considerations, some of the above NGCO CP elements have been further decomposed into internal building blocks. Fig. 3 depicts the SDN Coordinator’s internal functional architecture, containing the internal building blocks along with its NBIs and Southbound (SBI) interfaces as well as their interactions. It should be noted that each internal functional block can exploit the other building blocks’ functionalities while offering their own through the common service bus (blue bold line in Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. OCTAPUS NGCO SDN Coordinator internal functional architecture.

Table 1 briefly describes the role of each internal building block, whether a NBI is exposed (note that individual internal blocks can expose distinct NBIs; hence, the term “Northbound interfaces” in Fig. 3) and the specific functionalities exposed through it.

Table 1. Functionalities exposed by SDN Coordinator’s functional internal blocks.

SDN Coordinator building block	Brief description of high-level functionalities supported	Purpose of exposing NBI
NGCO Topology	Provides high-level information about the status of elements in the NGCO.	Retrieval of information about topology, links, and nodes. Updating of topology elements (e.g., node removal).
NGCO Provisioning	Lifecycle management of the different TSN and BE flows within the NGCO.	Retrieval of TSN and BE flow information (e.g., status, constraints etc.). Creation, removal, and update of TSN/BE flows.
Path Computation Engine (PCE)	Computation of path from source to destination within the NGCO.	Internal to the SDN Coordinator, no NBI exposed.
CUC	Entry point for the TSN Talker(s) and Listener(s) to create, update and remove TSN flows.	Creation, modification and removal of TSN flows.

NGCO Monitoring	Provides statistics about the various flows and their status.	Retrieval of the metrics related to traffic flows traversing the NGCO
Southbound Interface	Needed to interact with the different SDN Controllers.	The SBI functionalities are not exposed through the NBI but exploited by some NGCO functional components.
NGCO Re-routing	Allows the human-assisted re-routing of the traffic based on rule-based policies.	Creation, retrieval, and deletion of rule-based policies for traffic rerouting.

The SDN Coordinator NBI is mainly employed by the Management System and the Talker/Listener entities to provide the network administrator/user with a graphical representation of the functionalities exposed through the NBI itself. Along with the SDN Coordinator, the OCS SDN Controller consists of a specialized set of internal blocks tailored to manage and control the optical domain within the NGCO architecture. Fig. 4 illustrates the internal building blocks of the OCS SDN Controller, outlining the NBI/SBI, along with the primary internal interactions.

Fig. 4. OCS SDN Controller functional blocks, Northbound and Southbound Interfaces.

Table 2 delineates the functionalities exposed by the internal building blocks of the OCS SDN Controller, offering a detailed insight into the interfaces and capabilities facilitating seamless communication and control within the optical domain.

Table 2. Functionalities exposed by OCS SDN Controller functional internal blocks.

OCS SDN Controller Building Block	High-level functionality (Brief Description)	Purpose of exposing NBI
OCS Topology	Provides comprehensive information about the PCM optical elements.	OCS topology information retrieval and updating (PCMs, links, and node states).
OCS Provisioning	Manages the lifecycle of OCS configuration within the NGCO.	Optical circuit information (e.g., bandwidth, status, constraints). Creation, removal, and update of optical flows.

OCS Monitoring	Provides statistics about the performance and status of optical circuits.	Retrieval of metrics related to the active optical circuits within the NGCO.
Southbound Interface	Interaction with optical devices, specifically the PCMs comprising the OCS.	Configures the OCS, its interfaces, and the status of each PCM of the OCS.
OCS Re-routing	Enables human-assisted rerouting of traffic based on rule-based policies.	Creation, retrieval, and deletion of rule-based policies for optical traffic rerouting.

In contrast to the SDN Coordinator, the OCS SDN Controller utilizes its NBIs to expose its functionalities to external entities (i.e., the SDN Coordinator), encompassing detailed information regarding the optical domain topology and configurations. The OCS SDN Controller plays a crucial role in ensuring efficient and dynamic control over the optical domain. Specifically, it orchestrates the PCMs comprising the OCS and performing the actual backplane switching, a function that significantly impacts all NGCO-internal connections. In the end, this control capability allows the OCS SDN Controller to efficiently connect different TSN-enabled IF cards with Uplink switches, contributing to dynamic load balancing of traffic based on decisions formulated by the SDN Coordinator.

The OCS SDN Agent, with its three main functional internal blocks depicted in Fig. 5, acts as a critical intermediary between the higher-level SDN Controller and the OCS hardware. Table 3 provides a comprehensive overview of the internal building blocks of the OCS SDN Agent, outlining their high-level functionalities and corresponding interfaces exposed for interaction.

Fig. 5. OCS SDN Agent internal functional blocks.

Table 3. Functionalities exposed by OCS SDN Agent functional internal blocks.

OCS SDN Agent Block	High-level Functionality/ Brief Description	Northbound Interface Exposed for
NBI	Exposes configuration and monitoring interfaces to the OCS SDN Controller.	Exposes configuration parameters and monitoring data of the OCS to the OCS SDN Ctrl.

Engine	Configures the OCS, manages its interfaces, and controls internal PCM switching.	Offers configuration interfaces and monitoring for OCS interfaces, and PCMs.
SBI	Interacts with the OCS hardware, sending low-level commands to the OCS FPGA.	Facilitates communication with the OCS hardware.

The NBI serves as a crucial link between the OCS SDN Agent and the OCS SDN Controller, offering an interface for OCS configuration and monitoring. The Engine logic layer plays a pivotal role in configuring the OCS, managing its interfaces, and orchestrating the internal PCM switching. It offers configuration interfaces for adjusting OCS parameters and interfaces, while also providing robust monitoring functionalities to track the status of the OCS. The SBI acts as the bridge between the OCS SDN Agent and the OCS hardware, facilitating direct communication by transmitting low-level commands to the FPGA-based OCS controller responsible for creating the control waveforms for the PCM devices. This interface ensures precise control over the hardware, enabling seamless integration of the OCS into the SDN-controlled environment.

3 Network/Service provisioning within OCTAPUS

To illustrate the OCTAPUS NGCO's flexibility in dynamically supporting multiple concurrent fixed and mobile services with diverse QoS requirements, we have selected a typical European urban area in the city of Paris comprising the districts ("arrondissements") 14 and 15. The area under study is a highly touristic area, including residential and business/industrial building blocks and large open spaces being interconnected through a dense transportation network. The area covers 14.123 km² with a population of 366,112 [16]. We consider the following concrete usage scenarios:

- Everyday traffic during rush hour (US1): Normal usage of 5G/6G services at high mobility conditions (rush hour) e.g., 8-9 am, when people commute to work.
- Everyday traffic during busy hour (US2): High usage of 5G/6G services during or after working hours (e.g., 12am -1pm and 7-8 pm, respectively)
- Everyday traffic during night hours (US3): Low usage of 5G/6G services during night hours (e.g., 2-5am), when most people are asleep at home.

We have made the following assumptions in calculating the area traffic demands:

- With 4 operators, 75% of the population are fixed or wireless service subscribers.
- Smart city and massive IoT services cover only 25% of the area (1 device per m²).
- 75% percent of the mobile subscribers are served by eNodeB/gNodeB/Small Cells with a backhaul connection to the Core, while the remaining 25% are served by RUs with fronthaul connections to Baseband Units (BBUs).
- Within this area, a different mix of people is commuting, working or staying at home due to typical temporal variations of human activities, as shown in Table 4.

The targeted services to be offered to the subscribers include:

Legacy services: standard voice/data services whose requirements can be met by legacy 4G networks for everyday business requirements.

High capacity eMBB services: Uploading/streaming of UHD videos in private/public clouds, location-based VR/AR applications, high-definition IP TV etc.

mMTC services: massive IoT and smart city services.

URLLC services: smart grid services, advanced healthcare (e.g., smart ambulances, remote surgery), intelligent transportation systems, autonomous vehicle navigation.

X-haul services: dominated by fronthaul transport traffic between BBUs and RUs.

Enhanced Fiber Broadband: Ultra-high capacity (i.e., 25 Gbps) PON-based access allowing for telework, tele-education, etc. services' provisioning.

Table 4. Population, location and mobility assumptions for the different Usage Scenarios.

	US1	US2	US3
% added population (e.g., in transit through area)	10%	10%	0%
Actual present population in rush/busy/night hours	402,722	402,722	366,111
% population commuting (mobility)	50%	10%	5%
Actual population commuting (mobility)	201,361	40,272	18,306
% population at home	20%	20%	92%
Actual population at home	80,544	80,544	336,822
% population at offices/businesses	30%	70%	3%
Actual population at offices/businesses	120,817	281,905	10,983

A detailed calculation of the capacity requirements for the above services is provided in [17], the results of which are depicted in Table 5.

Table 5. Capacity Requirements for the Usage Scenarios.

Usage Scenario	Downstream capacity (Gbps)	Upstream capacity (Gbps)	Total capacity (Gbps)
US1: Rush Hour	16,782.9	49,377.2	66,128.1
US2: Busy Hour	75,709.6	116,709.6	192,387.2
US3: Night Hour	4,194.0	3,922.1	8,084.1

Fig. 6 illustrates the flexible connectivity options offered by OCTAPUS for both fixed and mobile subscribers, where solid lines denote actual fiber links and dotted lines are used to represent the actual E2E paths of the DP traffic from the cloud and/or the mobile core network, through the OCTAPUS NGCO, all the way to the Base Station antenna and/or the fixed subscribers. Fig. 6 also depicts two major installations with very high traffic demands (enclosed in the upper left and lower right ovals, respectively, in Fig. 6). In this case, the NGCO provides ultra-high-speed (up to 50 Gbps) PON access all the way up to the optical splitter installed at the local premises or for URLLC services with very tight latency requirements (e.g., close to 1 ms), the NGCO may even statically allocate/reserve an Express path for the installation.

The OCTAPUS NGCO can offer multiple types of X-haul connections to i) gNodeBs and high-functional-split RUs via PON (yellow and gray lines in Fig. 6), ii)

CPRI-based RUs, either via Point-to-Point links through the NGCO's Express paths or via eCPRI gateways (blue lines in Fig. 6), iii) a dedicated IF card connecting to a single RU for Gbps CPRI-based fronthaul, or direct connectivity between RUs and DUs/CUs bypassing the NGCO (light green lines in Fig. 6) and possibly allowing for the NGCO to be put in "sleep" mode in cases of low traffic demands [18].

Fig. 6. Representative urban area showcase OCTAPUS network architecture.

All of the above connectivity options are enabled by the SDN-controlled, (re)configurable OCS, which either routes the traffic through the NGCO, where load balancing among the NGCO's ULs can be initiated by the SDN Coordinator or bypasses the NGCO completely. The creation of network slices, either in advance, if the operator can predict service demand (i.e., for scheduled events, festivals) or dynamically in time is also driven by the SDN Coordinator, while time-sensitive services (such as the URLLC ones) are handled via the establishment of TSN streams via the CUC/SDN Coordinator/CNC chain. Although not shown in Fig. 6, the SDN Coordinator can also adapt to the time-varying capacity demands captured in Table 5 (particularly the low night hour values of US3) by selectively allowing access nodes serving low traffic to bypass the NGCO and obtain service from more remote NGCOs.

The above discussion indicates the crucial role of the NGCO CP in meeting the diverse service requirements, as well as the impact of the SDN Coordinator on orchestrating the NGCO's operation.

4 Conclusions

This paper presented the novel NGCO architecture proposed by the OCTAPUS project and described how it addresses the limitations of current COs in terms of flexibility to support multiple concurrent services with diverse QoS requirements, especially with regards to time-sensitive services which require TSN support and provisioning. All

major functional blocks of the OCTAPUS NGCO Data and Control Planes were described, including their roles and interactions. The capacity and latency requirements were estimated for a concrete example urban area for different usage scenarios including multiple emerging fixed and mobile services that the NGCO shall support concurrently by dynamically adapting to traffic variations and latency needs.

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